

CHARGE AND STABILITY OF COLLOIDS. PART VIII. KINETICS OF COAGULATION OF $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ SOL WITH AND WITHOUT ADDITION OF NON-ELECTROLYTE

BY B. P. YADAVA AND A. C. CHATTERJI

The effect of methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, sugar, agar-agar and gelatine has been studied with $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol. In the case of methyl alcohol the β values increase with increasing quantities, showing sensitisation and with other non-electrolytes decrease indicating protection. It has been found that βt remains constant, where t is the time required to reach a fixed stage of coagulation with increasing quantities of any non-electrolyte. A distinction between slow and rapid coagulation has been drawn on this.

In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 227) it has been shown that methyl alcohol accelerates whereas ethyl alcohol, sugar, gelatine and agar-agar retard the coagulation velocity of As_2S_3 sol. In this paper the influence of the above non-electrolytes has been studied with ferric hydroxide sol.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Ferric hydroxide sol was prepared by the method given in a previous communication of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 25). The method of procedure for the determination of the coagulation velocity was exactly the same as given in the previous paper. The results obtained are given below and plotted in Fig. 1.

Conc. of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol = 12 g./litre (as Fe_2O_3). Chlorine content of the sol = 0.016 g./litre Hence purity of the sol ($\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Cl}$) = 750.

TABLE I

5 C.c. of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol + 1 c.c. of 0.07N- K_2SO_4 + 4 c.c. of water.

Time.	$a-x$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.
0 min.	0.060	0.00	0.00
5	0.051	16.90	35.29
10	0.044	16.80	36.36
15	0.040	15.00	33.33
20	0.037	13.70	31.08
25	0.034	13.14	30.59
30	0.032	12.32	29.18

In the following tables the column $a-x$, has been deleted to conserve space in order to condense the tables.

TABLE II

5 C.c. of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol + increasing quantity of methyl alcohol + 1 c.c. of 0.07 N- K_2SO_4 + requisite volume of water to make up to 10 c.c.

Time.	M e t h y l a l c o h o l							
	1 c.c.		2 c.c.		3 c.c.		4 c.c.	
	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.
5 min.	200.0	599.9	229.8	723.2	278.1	942.7	349.8	1300
10	133.55	445.40	173.9	650.0	192.8	757.2	230.3	990.9
15	105.50	377.9	128.5	504.8	144.13	599.9	231.5	1267
20	82.90	303.0	101.95	411.7	123.20	550.0	195.0	1150
25	69.56	260.0	86.50	360.0	115.12	560.0	179.12	1160
30	64.30	252.4	76.8	330.3	104.70	538.0	149.3	996.5

TABLE III

5 C.c. of Fe(OH)₃ sol + increasing quantity of ethyl alcohol + 1 c.c. of 0.07 N-K₂SO₄ + requisite volume of water to make up to 10 c.c.

Time.	E t h y l a l c o h o l							
	1 c.c.		2 c.c.		3 c.c.		4 c.c.	
	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.
5 min.	146.5	400.0	130.3	345.5	109.9	280.1	87.7	213.8
10	114.9	361.6	100.0	300.0	87.9	253.0	73.25	200.0
15	89.3	297.0	76.6	241.0	66.6	200.0	58.6	168.6
20	72.50	250.0	66.8	222.7	53.5	164.3	46.8	137.5
25	63.30	226.7	58.0	200.0	46.0	144.6	38.7	114.9
30	57.96	216.6	52.75	188.9	41.20	133.3	33.3	100.0

TABLE IV

5 C.c. of Fe(OH)₃ sol + increasing quantity of sugar (10%) + 1 c.c. of 0.07 N-K₂SO₄ + requisite volume of water to make up to 10 c.c.

Time.	S u g a r s o l u t i o n (10%)							
	1 c.c.		2 c.c.		3 c.c.		4 c.c.	
	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.
5 min.	200.0	600.0	155.4	432.1	130.3	345.5	116.2	300.0
10	158.25	566.8	123.6	400.0	100.0	300.0	82.6	233.4
15	128.5	504.8	105.5	377.9	82.4	266.7	66.7	200.0
20	108.1	450.0	84.4	303.0	66.8	222.7	57.5	180.8
25	98.6	440.0	69.6	260.0	58.0	200.0	49.4	160.0
30	82.1	366.7	64.3	252.4	52.75	188.9	44.5	148.5

TABLE V

5 C.c. of Fe(OH)₃ sol + increasing quantity of gelatine (0.25%) + 1 c.c. of 0.07 N-K₂SO₄ + requisite volume of water to make up to 10 c.c.

Time.	G e l a t i n e s o l u t i o n (0.25%)							
	1 c.c.		2 c.c.		3 c.c.		4 c.c.	
	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.
5 min.	78.30	187.10	65.72	152.95	58.20	133.3	58.20	133.30
10	43.86	106.90	41.75	100.00	32.86	76.47	30.90	71.42
15	34.62	87.19	32.70	81.48	26.10	62.36	23.24	54.55
20	30.80	80.44	27.45	70.02	21.90	53.46	20.72	50.00
25	26.05	69.10	24.62	64.36	20.80	52.31	19.60	48.89
30	23.01	61.92	21.72	57.58	18.30	50.00	18.32	46.68

TABLE VI

5 C.c. of Fe(OH)₃ sol + increasing quantity of agar-agar (0.25%) + 1 c.c. of 0.07 N-K₂SO₄ + requisite volume of water to make up to 10 c.c.

Time.	A g a r - a g a r (0.25%)							
	1 c.c.		2 c.c.		3 c.c.		4 c.c.	
	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.
5 min.	58.20	133.80	51.30	115.8	48.10	107.65	39.04	85.72
10	37.00	87.53	32.86	76.47	29.10	66.66	25.66	57.89
15	29.24	71.27	26.10	62.36	23.24	54.55	20.66	47.61
20	27.39	70.02	23.18	57.14	21.90	43.76	19.66	46.78
25	24.62	64.36	20.80	52.31	18.54	45.71	17.50	42.77
30	23.00	61.92	18.32	46.68	17.30	43.39	16.30	40.74

DISCUSSION

With $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol the β values show a distinct tendency to fall with time in the case of all the non-electrolytes for any concentration of these non-electrolytes, but all these curves are alike. Here also we find with methyl alcohol that β increases for the same time interval whereas with other non-electrolytes it decreases with increasing quantities of the non-electrolytes added.

The values of $a-x$, the uncoagulated mass can also be plotted with increase in time and it can be observed that in the case of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol these curves become steeper with non-electrolytes than the one without non-electrolytes, including methyl alcohol, but with the latter the curves are different from the rest in so far that methyl alcohol increases the steepness of the curve with increase in the concentration whereas with other non-electrolytes the slope of the curves decreases as their concentration increases. From this it appears that methyl alcohol produces a different effect than other non-electrolytes, which is to be expected from its sensitisation effect.

From the values given in the above tables, $(a-x)-t$ and $\beta-t$ curves have been obtained. From these figures we can find out the time required to produce a definite stage of coalescence, e.g., we find t values for a fixed value of $(a-x)$. After knowing these t values we can read from $\beta-t$ curves the corresponding β values. From the values so found graphically, the product βt has been calculated and recorded in the following table.

TABLE VII

βt values with varying quantities of non-electrolytes.

Quantities of the non-electrolyte	As_2S_3 sol.				$(a-x) \times 10^3$	$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol.				$(a-x) \times 10^3$
	1 c.c.	2 c.c.	3 c.c.	4 c.c.		1 c.c.	2 c.c.	3 c.c.	4 c.c.	
Methyl alcohol	416.0	439.6	425.5	420.0	9	1334	1523	1474	1440	1.0
Ethyl alcohol	238.0	214.2	241.5	252.0	12	1045	1000	986	999	1.5
Sugar (10%)	116.2	142.5	104.0	120.0	15	1000	1043	1000	952	1.5
Gelatine (0.25%)	57.5	58.5	58.0	56.2	16.5	455	415	416	451	3.0
Agar-agar (0.25%)	157.5	99.75	128.0	128.0	15.0	412.5	412.5	409.5	416.3	3.0

FIG. 1
 $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol.

The above values of βt calculated from the $(a-x)$ values are not for the same stage of coagulation with all the non-electrolytes.

The stage of coagulation has to be different with different non-electrolytes depending on the nature of the curves, but with each non-electrolyte there is a fixed stage of coagulation.

From Table VII we see that the product βt remains almost constant, though the β values go on changing with time in the case of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol. From the equation

$$\tau_1 = \frac{\tau_0}{(\mathbf{I} + \beta t)^2} \quad \text{or} \quad \beta = \frac{\mathbf{I}}{t} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\tau_0}{\tau_1} - \mathbf{I}} \right)$$

it is clear that in order to make β values constant for various values of t we must have the relation between $\tau_1' : \tau_1'' : \tau_1''' : \tau_1''''$ etc., the number of primaries after the time t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4 etc., as follows :

$$\tau_1' : \tau_1'' : \tau_1''' : \tau_1'''' :: \frac{\mathbf{I}}{(\mathbf{I} + \beta t_1)^2} : \frac{\mathbf{I}}{(\mathbf{I} + \beta t_2)^2} : \frac{\mathbf{I}}{(\mathbf{I} + \beta t_3)^2} : \frac{\mathbf{I}}{(\mathbf{I} + \beta t_4)^2}$$

The above ratios give us the decrease in the values of τ_1 , when the times are varying, but β does not remain constant in slow coagulation and hence the decrease in τ_1 is slower than that indicated by the above relation.

On the other hand, when τ_1 is given a fixed value in the equation

$$\tau_1 = \frac{\tau_0}{(\mathbf{I} + \beta t)^2}$$

We can see that βt should remain constant, irrespective of the variation in t . Therefore if we can find out the time necessary to produce a fixed stage of coagulation *i.e.*, the time required to reach a fixed value of τ_1 , we should find that βt is constant. This is exactly what is found from the above experiments. Therefore we are justified in saying that the kinetics of coagulation in the above experiments have proceeded in accordance with Smoluchowski's theory.

Smoluchowski suggested that the equation

$$\tau_1 = \frac{\tau_1}{(\mathbf{I} + \beta t)^2} \quad \text{should be} \quad \tau_1 = \frac{\tau_0}{(\mathbf{I} + \epsilon \beta t)^2} \quad \text{for slow coagulation}$$

we can put $\epsilon \beta = B$, where B is the β value for slow coagulation.

We have seen that B changes with time but the time required to bring about a definite stage of coalescence is proportional to B values *i.e.* t varies inversely as B .

Therefore, $t_1 B_1 = t_2 B_2 = t_3 B_3 = t_4 B_4$ etc.,

or $t_1 \epsilon_1 B = t_2 \epsilon_2 B = t_3 \epsilon_3 B = t_4 \epsilon_4 B$ etc., where B is the velocity of coagulation when no non-electrolyte is added,

or $t_1 \epsilon_1 = t_2 \epsilon_2 = t_3 \epsilon_3 = t_4 \epsilon_4$ etc.,

or $t_1 : t_2 : t_3 : t_4 :: \frac{\mathbf{I}}{\epsilon_1} : \frac{\mathbf{I}}{\epsilon_2} : \frac{\mathbf{I}}{\epsilon_3} : \frac{\mathbf{I}}{\epsilon_4}$ etc.

This means that the reciprocal of the time required to produce a definite stage of coalescence is proportional to ϵ , the probability factor. We know that probability factor varies, and from the above it is clear that ϵ varies inversely as the time required to bring about the same stage of coagulation. Therefore we can say that the difference between the rapid and the slow coagulation is this that in rapid coagulation the β values remain constant and further βt is also constant for the same stage of coagulation, it means that the time required to bring about the same stage of coagulation will be the same when various electrolytes are added. In slow coagulation region as β decreases, and further here also βt remains constant, the time required to reach the same stage of coagulation will proportionately increase, so that Smoluchowski's theory gives that in the slow coagulation region β must decrease but the decrease in β must be proportional to the increase in t , the time required to reach the same stage of coagulation in a set of experiments, whereas in the region of rapid coagulation both β and the time required to produce the same stage of coagulation remain constant (*cf.* Mukherjee and Papacoustantinou, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **117**, 1563).

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY.

Received May 18, 1944.
